

A Security-Enhanced Interoperability Middleware for the Internet of Things

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Abstract—This paper documents an Internet of Things (IoT) middleware specially tailored to address the security, and operational requirements expected from an effective IoT platform. In essence, the middleware exposes a diverse palette of features, including authentication, authorization, auditing, confidentiality and integrity of data. Besides these aspects, the middleware encapsulates an IoT object abstraction layer that builds a generic object model that is independent from the device type (i.e., hardware, software, vendor). Furthermore, it builds on standards and specifications to accomplish a highly resilient and scalable solution. The approach is tested on several hardware platforms. A use case scenario is presented to demonstrate its main features. The middleware represents a key component in the context of the “GHOST - Safe-Guarding Home IoT Environments with Personalised Real-time Risk Control” project.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, home automation, security, authentication, authorization, scalability

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) brings upon a new infrastructural paradigm, where network objects are individually connected to the Internet, and are accessible via unique identifiers. Undoubtedly, a key enabler that rises to meet this technological challenge is the underlying wireless communications technology. Accordingly, the growing popularity and ubiquitous presence of WiFi, ZigBee, and Z-Wave constitute an indisputable proof on the sustained progress towards achieving this technological revolution.

While the IoT’s core concept, architectural requirements, and enabling technologies have been intensively analyzed [1], [2], [3], [4], the security-aware design of an IoT platform enabling interoperability for heterogeneous devices and technologies, has received less attention from the scientific community. Nevertheless, recently, promising progress has been recorded in this direction as well [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10]. A common understanding of these works is the need to secure the data exchanges between various “objects” (i.e., sensors, actuators, and users) via a few commonly acknowledged requirements: confidentiality, integrity, availability, authentication, and authorization. A notable aspect of the aforementioned requirements is that they apply to the actual data exchanges and to the objects issuing/receiving the data. However, we observe that, while a large number of IoT platforms have been proposed, few cases address the security from this perspective. In fact, most of the times existing middleware address the security requirements via traditional transport layer security protocols (e.g., SSL/TLS), and user authentication techniques.

Conversely, we believe a more significant focus needs to be placed on the security of interactions between “object”, the very essence of the IoT.

According to the above-mentioned issues and requirements analysis, this paper presents the building blocks of a security-enhanced interoperability middleware for the Internet of Things. The middleware exposes a diverse palette of features, including authentication, authorization, auditing, confidentiality and integrity of data. Besides these aspects, the middleware encompasses an IoT object abstraction layer that builds a generic object model, which is independent from the physical device type (i.e., hardware, software, vendor). Furthermore, the middleware builds on standards and specifications to accomplish a highly resilient and scalable solution. The approach has been tested on several hardware platforms. A use case scenario is presented to demonstrate its main features.

The middleware has been developed as part of project “GHOST - Safe-Guarding Home IoT Environments with Personalised Real-time Risk Control” (<https://www.ghost-iot.eu/>). The project aims at developing innovative solutions for: i) increasing the automation level and efficiency of existing security services for IoT; ii) providing cybersecurity ‘blackbox’ for customers with effortless decision support and advanced usable transparency; and iii) safeguarding critical data using blockchain technology.

This document is structured as follows. Section II provides a brief overview on related studies. Then, Section III presents the properties and architecture of the proposed middleware. A case study analysing a realistic IoT application realised with the proposed middleware is presented in Section IV and the report concludes in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

In the scientific literature we find a plethora of IoT platforms coming from industry as well as from academia. This section provides a brief synthesis on the most recently proposed platforms. A more complete analysis can be found in related surveys [1], [5], [10], [8], [11].

In general, based on previous surveys, and literature review, we observe that IoT platforms can be grouped in two major categories: i) cloud-based systems in which the IoT devices or the device gateways directly connect to a public cloud through the Internet [16]; and ii) standalone platforms, enabling local installations, usually encompassing one or more IoT gateways [17].

DIMMER [12] is a distributed Web application-based smart city platform providing device abstraction, a scalable, and resilient architecture. FarmBeats [13] is an IoT platform for data-driven agriculture collecting data from sensors, cameras, and drones, while providing strong availability, cloud support, and data freshness. Spanò, *et al.* [14] developed the Last-Meter platform, which aims at delivering the technical solution for integrating the Smart Grid into IoT platforms. It provides support for heterogeneous sensor communication protocols, secure and differentiated access to data, alongside an abstraction layer for sensors, and actuators. The SMARTIE project [15] aims at creating a secure framework for IoT-based smart city applications, considering the confidentiality, integrity and availability security requirements.

VIRTUS [18] is an IoT middleware combining the Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP) with OSGi technology to provide secure event-driven communications within an IoT scenario. It relies on the provided security features of XMPP and supports the isolated operation.

Xively [19] is a cloud-based platform focusing on the acquisition, storage and management of data-streams collected from various sensors. It provides a Web-based access to the collected data which is stored on Xively servers. This platform provides authorization using API (Application Programming Interface) keys.

openHAB [20] is an OSGi based-open source home automation software that is mainly dedicated for centralized home automation units (i.e., gateways). While designed to be “absolutely vendor-neutral as well as hardware/protocol-agnostic”, it does not define a device feature abstraction. openHAB integrates an increased number of device families and protocols through named bindings. It provides support for cloud-based access, but it can also be used locally in an isolated environment without cloud integration. openHAB provides a powerful scenario engine based on a custom script language and there are several available client applications which provide access for users to interact with the devices on desktop and mobile devices.

Compared to previous studies and developments, the middleware presented in this work is similar to openHAB. However, while our proposal defines an abstraction for device features based on open standards, each openHAB binding supports user-defined (i.e., non-standardized) and heterogeneous features. Furthermore, openHAB is restricted to Java, while the proposed middleware supports various programming languages. Due to its design, the proposed middleware can run in various contexts on different platforms ranging from small home gateways to data centers (i.e., the cloud).

III. THE DEVELOPED MIDDLEWARE

The middleware is a software platform to *securely* connect and manage different types of endpoints, from physical devices (e.g., switches, sensors, surveillance cameras), to users. The platform addresses several major issues specific to the IoT domain, including: i) *flexible communications*; ii) *secure* data exchanges; and iii) *integration* of heterogeneous IoT devices.

In terms of communications, the middleware supports data exchanges between different types of objects: i) *human to device* communication by exposing device functionalities (e.g., control, events, and states) through Internet and retrieving device history (e.g., events); ii) *device to device* communication used in the context of various scenarios, which allows automatic interactions between devices without human intervention; and iii) *human to human* communication mainly useful for enterprise installations for internal data exchanges (e.g., instant messaging, video conferencing).

In terms of security features, the middleware embraces: i) communication *encryption* (i.e., integrity and confidentiality); ii) *authentication* of the users and things connected to the system; iii) *authorization* of the operations upon resources with high grain permissions indicating the permitted user operations; and iv) *auditing* of the operations upon resources. A notable aspect of the proposed middleware is that access to all stored data (e.g., device events, user activity events) is authorized, while all the data exchanges are conducted over private channels, which results in strong privacy.

At its core, the main technological enabler of the middleware is the Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol (XMPP) [21], and its associated architecture. This brings upon numerous benefits, including:

- 1) an *open* IETF standard based on XML, which is also the adopted standard for instant message and presence communication within the open source community;
- 2) a *decentralized* and *scalable* distributed architecture, similar to the e-mailing system, which easily scales both horizontally and vertically;
- 3) a *cross-domain interoperability* layer, where distinct domains managed by different entities are seamlessly interconnected (e.g., devices managed by different companies can interact);
- 4) an *extensible* architecture, where the designed protocol is easily extended, and a large variety of *extensions* are available for different types of applications;
- 5) a *publish-subscribe* communication paradigm for lightweight distribution of events;
- 6) a secure communication layer that leverages the TLS standard and *authentication* using various mechanisms (e.g., SASL, external LDAP).

The remainder of this section provides a detailed presentation on the middleware’s architecture and its main features.

A. Architecture

At the highest level of the middleware multiple XMPP domains (servers) can be interconnected over the Internet (see Fig. 1). These represent the infrastructure’s “backbone”, which route the messages between entities (e.g., users, physical devices), an approach that is similar to the traditional emailing system. The distribution of the XMPP domains ensures the proper load distribution and interconnection between resources managed by different authorities.

Inside each XMPP domain the IoT-specific features are implemented in server-side components by leveraging the

Fig. 1. Middleware architecture

XEP-0114: Jabber Component Protocol. An XMPP component assures a modular extension of XMPP servers, such that components operate independently, yet tightly interconnected with the associated server. The components are addressable via the sub-domain of the server’s domain name.

The XMPP server is the “gateway” to the Internet and provides authentication, encryption and message routing capabilities. On the other hand, the XMPP component provides the dedicated IoT features (detailed in the following sections) for its associated entities (e.g., IoT devices, automation scenarios).

The entities present within the middleware are *nodes* uniquely identified by a UUID (Universally Unique Identifier). The UUID, together with the domain name forms the node’s JID (Jabber ID). The JID is used in all message exchanges between nodes. The following aspects are specific to a *node*: i) it exposes a set of properties (e.g., the capabilities of the associated device); ii) it receives commands and can respond to such commands (e.g., getting and setting the state of a device); and iii) it can generate events (e.g., state change events).

Internally, the middleware builds on several software agents interconnected through ZeroMQ [22] channels. In this ensemble, each agent has a distinct role (e.g., internal message routing between the agents, abstracting a particular IoT protocol, automating the execution of scenarios). Agents are implemented using the most suitable programming language (conditioned by the support for ZeroMQ). Accordingly, this architecture offers modularity, flexibility, scalability, and redundancy.

B. IoT Device Abstraction

To communicate with the IoT devices (e.g, get sensor measurements, set actuators, receive events from the devices) the middleware defines the *device protocol* as an extension to the XMPP standard. This provides an abstract layer of communication with various devices provided by different vendors using distinct communication protocols. In this context a

device is a hardware equipment, whose state can be monitored and optionally changed by the middleware. A device can support multiple features, not necessarily related to each other. However, each feature must be unique per *node*. Accordingly, *nodes* can also embrace and abstract the features of several *devices*, and, a *device* can be represented by several *nodes*.

The middleware defines a series of *features* that can be used for mapping different IoT devices (e.g., alarm, battery, color, current, demand-temperature, energy, gps, pressure, state, switch, temperature). Each *feature* has a series of properties: i) states; ii) value range; iii) unit; and iv) reading/writing/event capabilities. For example, the *switch* feature is readable, writable, it generates events, it has *on* and *off* states, while the *temperature* feature is only readable and generates events, while its value is a float expressed in Celsius.

The following example shows how an abstracted temperature can be queried using the XMPP protocol. In order to retrieve the value of the *temperature* feature, the user `romeo@example.net` sends the following request to the node `e08c401d-dc3f-4859-8215-c1362a532fa0` attached to the middleware within the domain `middleware.example.com`:

```
<iq
  type="get "
  from="romeo@example.net "
  to="e08c401d-dc3f-4859-8215-
    c1362a532fa0@middleware.example.com"
  id="ab1c">
  <temperature xmlns="urn:hermess:device"/>
</iq>
```

The node then responds with the following message:

```
<iq
  type="result"
  from="e08c401d-dc3f-4859-8215-
    c1362a532fa0@middleware.example.com".
  to="romeo@example.net "
  id="ab1c">
  <temperature xmlns="urn:hermess:device"
    value="22.7"
    timestamp="2018-03-12T07:24:44Z"/>
</iq>
```

It can be seen that the response contains the temperature value, in Celsius (coming from the abstraction), and the time stamp of the measurement.

C. Middleware Properties

The main role of the middleware is to provide a secure, flexible and scalable infrastructure with communication channels between IoT devices and the users. However, besides this core functionality, the middleware also provides several advanced security properties.

1) *Authorization*: The middleware provides support for *authorization* (i.e., access control for the attached resources). The authorization mechanism uses the following concepts: i) *Object* is a resource towards which the access rights need to be verified; ii) *User* is an XMPP user accessing one or more objects; iii) *Admin* is an entity with administration rights in

charge of defining the authorization policies; iv) *Authorization manager* is a software module, in charge of managing permission policies; v) *Object manager* is a software module, which manages objects and enforces permission policies managed by an authorization manager; and vi) *Permission* groups the set of permitted operations for a specific user on a particular object.

In the process of authorization a *User* accesses an *Object* managed by an *Object Manager*. The *Object Manager* leverages the authorization information provided by the *Authorization Manager* to enforce permissions rights. The *Authorization Manager* stores the authorization policies which are defined by an *Admin* (administration entity). The communication between the *Object Manager* and *Authorization Manager* is performed using an XMPP-based protocol.

The authorization scheme described above provides increased flexibility, therefore it can be deployed using different approaches: i) one Authorization Manager used by multiple Object Managers; or ii) multiple cascaded Authorization Managers. Using the latter topology, an authorization request from an Object Manager is sent to the first level of the Authorization Manager, which can respond, if it possesses the required information, or it can forward the request to the next authorization level.

2) *History*: The various events generated by the middleware *nodes* are stored in the database for later retrieval. History events can represent a wide variety of activities in the context of the middleware: joining a session, broadcasting a video session, the triggering of an alarm, a switch turning on/off. The middleware provides a flexible process for event retrieval based on the time when the event was registered, or according to a more complex criteria based on the event's properties.

3) *Scheduler*: The middleware provides support for scheduling the state changes of specific *features*. This is realized by scheduled commands issued towards devices via the XMPP protocols. The scheduling is based on CRON expressions, which represent a set of intervals, or fixed time stamps when the scheduling needs to be triggered.

4) *Virtual Devices*: *Virtual devices* are *nodes* exposing device *features*. Compared to *nodes*, they are not bound to physical devices. Virtual devices are useful in several scenarios, such as:

- Aggregating the state of several nodes in order to build more complex abstractions. An example in this direction is a virtual thermostat device, which may use one temperature sensor to retrieve the ambient temperature, a switch to control the heating, and to expose a *demand-temperature* feature in order to set the desired temperature.
- To build device-specific scenarios. For instance, each night, at 2 AM, if the humidity is too low, switch on the sprinklers for 30 minutes.

D. Device Compatibility

The developed middleware supports multiple IoT device families and protocols (e.g., Z-Wave, KNX, Dali, Philips Hue, XComfort, Onvif, CibTech). For each family, it provides

abstract device representations and communication protocols (i.e., XMPP). For example, relay connected through the Z-Wave radio-based protocol can be switched using the same message (i.e., XMPP stanza) as it would in case of a wired relay module connected through the KNX protocol.

Besides the above-mentioned device families and protocols the middleware supports several other protocols. Furthermore, by design, it can be easily extended with additional protocols. For this purpose, a new software agent must be defined to implement the abstraction of the new devices and protocols and to perform the conversion between XMPP and the given device protocol. In the following, we provide two examples of existing device families and protocol integration.

1) *Z-Wave*: Z-Wave is a wireless communication protocol, mainly used for home automation. It is based on low-power, low-range mesh radio communication. The main advantage of Z-Wave in comparison with other wireless mesh networks for IoT (e.g., ZigBee) is the large number of available vendors producing a wide variety of certified interoperable sensors, actuators and smart objects. In the center of a Z-Wave network is the Z-Wave controller that manages the communication between devices. A Z-Wave network can consist of up to 232 devices of multiple types. The Z-Wave devices can be “always-on” devices or battery powered sleeping devices.

The middleware communicates with a Z-Wave network through dedicated interfaces (i.e., Z-Wave controllers), which expose the events from the Z-Wave network and forward the commands to the devices using an API. It has to be noted that not all the Z-Wave packets are forwarded through the Z-Wave controller. Instead only a predefined set of activities defined in the API can be executed. The middleware supports multiple types of Z-Wave interfaces: i) USB- or UART-based Z-Wave controllers integrated through the `OpenZWave` software stack; and ii) the CTS iCPE Z-Wave controller using the exposed API based on MQTT over XMPP communication.

2) *KNX*: KNX is a standardized wired and wireless communication protocol for building automation. The standard is designed to be independent of any particular hardware platform. The KNX-compatible devices are produced by KNX Association member companies and are interoperable through various physical communication medium (e.g., twisted pair wiring, radio (KNX-RF), Ethernet). The middleware communicates with KNX devices through KNX-to-Ethernet interfaces using the EIBnet/IP protocol.

E. IoT Gateway Compatibility

The middleware, by design, can be hosted on various system architectures (e.g., x86, amd64, armhf, arm64), operating systems (e.g., Linux, Windows) and distributions (e.g., Debian, OpenWRT). However, it has a series of software dependencies (e.g., third-party software, libraries) which must be resolved in order to enable its deployment on the target platform. The main operating system on which the middleware was tested is the Debian Stretch. However, its main features and components have also been tested on other OS. In the remainder of this

Fig. 2. Architecture of a realistic IoT application

Fig. 3. User interface of the Home Management Portal

section we detail the implementation of the middleware on two mainstream devices.

1) *Raspberry Pi*: Raspberry Pi is a single-board computer family offering with multiple communication interfaces. The middleware is compatible with Raspberry Pi version 2 and 3. These boards can be mounted with a *RaZberry Z-Wave* interface, which transforms them into full featured multi-protocol *Home IoT Hubs*. The resulted hubs support Z-Wave, Ethernet, USB, UART, GPIO communication protocols. In addition, version 3 of these boards also support Bluetooth and WiFi protocols. These protocols enable the pairing of various IoT devices, thus creating the premises for developing complex and feature-rich home IoT solutions.

The officially supported operating system for Raspberry Pi is *Raspbian*, a Debian-based Linux distribution. The Raspbian Stretch version is based on Debian Stretch, which is fully compatible with the proposed middleware.

The Raspberry Pi Home IoT Hubs were tested with the middleware with multiple types of IoT devices: i) Z-Wave devices connected through the *RaZBerry* interface and integrated through *OpenZWave*; ii) wired KNX equipments connected through an *Ethernet-to-KNX* interface; and iii) IoT devices connected through custom IP gateways (e.g., Philips Hue).

2) *CTS iCPE*: *iCPE* is a Z-Wave-to-IP gateway provided by CTS that exposes multiple communication interfaces (Ethernet, 3G/4G) using various communication protocols (MQTT, XMPP, REST) for granting access to the Z-Wave network. It is a Z-Wave static controller offering a rich set of features for Z-Wave network and device management, and for interacting with sensors and actuators.

The middleware is hosted on the *iCPE* following two approaches: i) running the middleware on the *iCPE* and communicating via *localhost* communication; and ii) connecting to an *iCPE* from the middleware hosted by a different system (e.g., Raspberry Pi).

IV. CASE STUDY

In this section we present a use case-based analysis to showcase the practical utilization of the middleware’s features and operation. Fig. 2 represents the architecture of the case study. We presume a home security and automation IoT infrastructure provisioned in the living home and in the “weekend house” of a particular user. The basic operational requirements for this system are: i) standalone functionality in both physical locations; ii) a unified and transparent access from the user’s point of view; and iii) security and privacy. Furthermore, in terms of required features we mention: i) modern home security system in both locations; ii) automated and remotely controllable heating and climate systems in both sites; and iii) automated and remotely controllable outdoor illumination within the premises of the weekend house.

To satisfy these requirements the installation leverages Z-Wave smart devices with two instances, each hosted by CTS *iCPE* home gateways. The two instances are configured in two distinct XMPP domains, are interconnected through a server-to-server connection. Consequently, all the resources are transparently addressable from both domains. In case of a communication failure between the two sites (i.e., Internet connectivity issues), the two sites continue the stable operation via the automation features of the local devices. In addition, a Home Management Portal is installed in the gateway located in the living home to provide a Web-based user interface for the home automation application and capabilities for configuring the system, the attached devices, and the automation scenarios. In Fig. 3 the user interface of such portal is shown.

To implement the required features, the Z-Wave sensors and actuators are used in cooperation with automation scenarios running in the middleware. For the home security system motion sensors, door/window sensors, and smoke, flood and CO sensors, produced by the *Fibaro Systems*, are mounted in the houses and all the alerts generated by these sensors are

forwarded to the user's mobile phone. The user can arm/disarm the houses using the mobile application. To control the heating and cooling system, and the lights in the houses relay modules are used.

The security and the privacy are enforced by combining multiple methods and mechanisms. In the first phase, all the XMPP domains expose a valid certificate signed by a Certification Authority, while all the communication lines are encrypted, and the endpoints are authenticated as follows: i) the client-to-jabber communication is encrypted using TLS, the user is authenticated through SASL mechanisms, while the Jabber server is authenticated using certificate-based mechanisms; ii) the jabber-to-component channels use TLS and the components use username- and password-based authentication; iii) the server-to-server connections also leverage TLS and certificates in both endpoints; and iv) the Z-Wave radio communication uses AES encryption, while the devices must be included into the Z-Wave network through a strict process that verifies device authenticity.

By leveraging the authorization mechanism of the middleware the accessing procedures of devices by each user are flexibly managed. A potential use-case is the following: i) the administrator user has rights for reading and modifying the states of all the resources in the system, and access all the configuration facilities; ii) a home user has only reading and modifying rights to all the attached devices; iii) guest users may have temporary reading and modifying access to the resources located in the weekend house; and iv) a user assigned to a security company can only read the states of the sensors.

Finally, the history feature of the middleware stores all the events and activities regarding the managed resources in the system (e.g., sensor measurements, actuator commands, user login), which provides a rich information set for auditing purposes.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work documented a middleware that provides availability, confidentiality, integrity, authentication, authorization and privacy for Internet of Things applications. The architecture of the middleware is highly modular, and it defines two abstraction layers: the *node* and the *virtual device* concepts. These aid the aggregation of various features, the definition of abstract, and complex devices. A notable characteristic of the developed middleware is its extensibility and scalability, which stem from the adoption of open standards and open source software. The compatibility of the middleware with respect to popular hardware was analyzed, and a use case-based scenario was presented to showcase the applicability of the middleware in practical scenarios.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is partially funded by the European Unions Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme through GHOST project (<https://www.ghost-iot.eu/>) under Grant Agreement No. 740923.

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